

Silicon recovery via the acid leaching of a Si-Ca-Al alloy produced by the SisAl process

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Keywords: Silicon, Impurity, Acid leaching, Purification, Microstructure

Abstract –The sustainable production of high-purity silicon is one of the greatest concerns in the solar industry. The SisAl process is an alternative and innovative approach to produce high-purity silicon based on aluminothermic reduction of silica in slags. In the present work, a Si-Ca-Al alloy was produced through SisAl aluminothermic reduction and further purified through acid leaching. The main precipitates of the Si-Ca-Al alloy were determined as CaSi_2 and CaAl_2Si_2 with minor other metallic phases embedded inside. The alloy was further crushed and milled for leaching experiments using hydrochloric acid under magnetic stirring. The concentration of impurities before and after leaching experiments were measured by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). After 3 hours leaching, 97.5% Ca, 97.1% Al, and 79.8% P were removed, while the silicon purity was upgraded from 75% to over 99%.

1. INTRODUCTION

In response to the increasingly severe situation of global climate change issue, carbon neutrality has become the leading environmental goal of the international community in the 21st Century. Accordingly, the application of renewable energy is booming worldwide to displace conventional fossil fuels. Despite the COVID-19 pandemic crisis, the global PV capacity annual addition had another record-breaking year in 2020 with approximately 139 GW and brought the global total PV capacity to an all-time high number of around 760 GW (*Renewables 2021 Global Status Report*, 2021). As the dominant material for the solar PV industry, silicon plays a significant role in transition to low carbons society.

Nowadays, metallurgical-grade silicon (MG-Si, purity 99%), as the feedstock for solar-grade silicon (SoG-Si, purity 99.9999%), is commercially produced through the carbothermic reduction of quartz with carbon reductant in a submerged arc furnace. However, due to the nature of the carbothermic reaction, greenhouse gas emission is unavoidable. In addition, the current production of SoG-Si is dominated by the modified Siemens process and fluidized bed reactor process, which is also known for high energy consumption and carbon footprint.(Murgau and Safarian, 2018). Thus, there is growing interest in developing more environmentally friendly processes for Si production.

The SisAl process is a patented novel industrial process to produce Si, Si-Al alloys, and alumina with different grades.(*www.sisal-pilot.eu*, 2021). It presents a strong contribution to the transformation towards a low carbon circular economy by utilizing secondary raw materials such as Al scrap and/or Al dross to replace the carbon reductants. In the SisAl process, the Al-source metallothermically reduces the SiO_2 from CaO-SiO₂ slag, and the products encompass Si alloy as the metal phase and CaO-Al₂O₃-(low) SiO₂ slag as the slag phase. The calcium aluminate slag can be further treated hydrometallurgically to produce metallurgical-grade alumina (MGA) and high-purity alumina (HPA), while the obtained Si-Ca-Al alloy can be upgraded to MG-Si and SoG-Si through further refining step.

Acid leaching has been found as an efficient and economical technique for Si refining in the past decades. Its mechanism is to dissolve the precipitates of the Si alloy in an acidic solution, and the remaining part is the dissolvable Si phase. To date, considerable work had been done on silicon purification through acid leaching of different Si alloy systems, including the binary system Si-Ca(Schei, 1985), Si-Mg(Espelien, Tranell and Safarian, 2017; Zhu, Azarov, *et al.*, 2020; Zhu, Ying Yue, *et al.*, 2020), Si-Al(Yoshikawa and Morita, 2003; Ban *et al.*, 2015), and the ternary systems as the binary combinations(Zhu, Wan, *et al.*, 2020). Sun *et al.*(Sun *et al.*, 2017) found that P enriched in the CaAl_2Si_2 phase in Si-30at%Al alloy. High P removal was achieved by Lai *et al.*(Lai *et al.*, 2018) on the leaching of a Si- 3.3 at%Ca-6.7 at%Al alloy. In our previous work(Zhu *et al.*, 2021), acid leaching of Si-Ca-Al alloys was studied with the Ca and Al concentrations lower than 5 wt%. It was found that the P removal efficiency depends on the Ca/Al ratio and the total alloying elements concentration. However, the Si-Ca-Al alloy obtained from the novel SisAl process lies in a unique composition range, and very rare information about the alloy is reported.

In the present work, a Si-Ca-Al alloy was obtained through the pilot scale SisAl aluminothermic reduction process. To determine the phases of the sample, the microstructure was first studied. Acid leaching experiments were designed to investigate the Si purification and recovery efficiency of the produced Si alloy.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The pilot-scale SisAl process test was operated at Elkem in Kristiansand, Norway. In the test, about 460 kg material were treated yielding a Si-Al-Ca alloy and a calcium aluminate slag.. After the aluminothermic reaction, the molten slag and metal were held for 1 hour at around 1600 °C. Then, the slag and metal were tapped out into a steel mould, and the obtained Si-Ca-Al alloy from the metal phase was crushed to lumps. To study the acid leaching of the obtained Si alloy, particle-size reduction of the alloy lumps was performed further by the Retsch Vibratory Disc Mill RS200 with the tungsten carbide units. Alloy lumps were milled to the target particle size of 1-5 mm for further investigation.

The microstructure of the studied Si-Ca-Al alloy was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and electron probe micro-analyzer (EPMA, JXA-8500F), and the wavelength-dispersive spectroscopy (WDS) was applied for the phase composition determination. Additionally, the phases of the ternary alloy were identified by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) using the Bruker D8 Focus X-ray Diffractometer with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation (wavelength of 1.54 Å). The X-ray diffraction test was performed from 5 to 90 deg diffraction angle and using a step size of 0.013 deg.

In the leaching process, 10.00 g Si-Ca-Al alloy particles were charged into 200 mL 10% HCl acidic solution at 60 °C on a hotplate. The leaching period lasted 3 hours. Mechanical stirring of the solution was performed by a magnetic stirrer with 300 rpm during the whole leaching process. After leaching, the beaker stood for another 10 min for better particle-solution separation and the solution was then poured out. Finally, the remaining particles were washed by ethanol three times. The particles were dried naturally without heating.

The chemical composition of the alloy samples before and after leaching was analyzed by Agilent 8800 triple quadrupole high resolution inductively coupled plasma mass spectroscopy (ICP-MS). The Si-Ca-Al alloy composition was listed in Table I.

Table I: Composition of the Si-Ca-Al alloy measured by ICP-MS.

Impurity	Concentration (ppmw)	Impurity	Concentration (ppmw)
Ca	149385	Ti	300
Al	90729	V	136
Mg	2141	P	12.4
Fe	4585	Ga	168
Mn	681	Si	751836

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Microstructure

The X-ray diffraction pattern of the Si-Ca-Al alloy is illustrated in Figure 1, which reveals that the main phases in the ternary alloy are Si, CaAl_2Si_2 and CaSi_2 . The microstructure of obtained Si-Ca-Al alloy was further examined by SEM and EPMA as shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, where the CaSi_2 and CaAl_2Si_2 precipitates were identified and with minor needle-like Fe-bearing phase, Fe_3Si_7 (Zhu *et al.*, 2021), embedded inside. The detected composition of each phase by WDS point analysis is listed in Table II. It can be seen that the precipitates also contain a certain level of other impurities. For instance, the CaSi_2 precipitate dissolves a small amount of Al and the Fe_3Si_7 phase contains more transition metal impurities like Ti and Mn.

As seen in Figure 2, the Si matrix formed from primary Si solidification exhibits a plate-like morphology with a thickness of around 200 μm . The CaSi_2 phase and CaAl_2Si_2 phase coexist to form the precipitates area, which can be further removed after the acid leaching process. Unlike the observed microstructure of Si-rich Si-Ca-Al alloy from our previous work (Zhu *et al.*, 2021), in the Si-Ca-Al alloy produced from the SisAl process, most of them exhibit lamellar eutectic patterns where the lamellas display similar growth directions and reflect the thermal gradient.

Figure 1: X-ray diffraction spectrum of the studied Si-Ca-Al alloy.

Figure 2: SEM images and microstructure of the studied Si-Ca-Al alloy.

Figure 3: EPMA elemental mapping results of the studied Si-Ca-Al alloy.

Table II: Measured composition in wt% of major phases in the studied Si-Ca-Al alloy by WDS point analysis.

Phase	Si	Ca	Al	Fe	Ti	Mn	Mg	P
Si	99.9	0.02	0.04	0.01	-	0.02	0.0007	-
CaSi ₂	56	43	0.9	0.1	-	0.01	0.2	0.01
CaAl ₂ Si ₂	36	27	37	0.003	0.003	0.01	0.2	0.02
Fe ₃ Si ₇	49	0.9	4.2	42.5	0.008	0.04	0.04	0.01

3.2 Leaching results

In the leaching process, the reactive precipitates CaSi₂ and CaAl₂Si₂ constantly dissolve into the HCl solution, and the impurities embedded inside are also separated from the remaining Si phase. The morphology evolution of Si alloy particles before and after leaching is presented in Figure 4. As shown in Figure 4(a), before leaching, the particles are coarse and contain plate-like Si phase in dark grey colour and surrounded by large number of precipitates with bright colour and the lamellar patterns. After leaching, the precipitates are removed, and the remaining particles are the purified Si with a significantly reduced particle size.

The leaching mechanism can be described by the following reactions (Vogg, Brandt and Stutzmann, 2003; Marot, Correia-Anacleto and Jocelyn Le, 2012):

And,

The impurity removal degree was calculated as below:

$$\eta = \frac{C_{initial} - C_{final}}{C_{initial}} \times 100\% \quad [3]$$

where $C_{initial}$ and C_{final} denote the impurity concentration before and after leaching.

Figure 4: SEM images of the studied Si-Ca-Al alloy particles (a) Before leaching (1-5 mm); (b) After acid leaching.

The leaching results of remaining impurities concentration and their removal degree from the Si-Ca-Al alloy are presented in Figure 5. It is seen that the impurity concentration continuously

decreases with increasing leaching time, especially in the first half an hour that nearly 90% of Ca and Al were removed. After 3 hours of leaching, the Ca concentration was reduced from 14.94wt% to 0.37 wt%, indicating a removal degree of 97.5%, while Al concentration decreased from 9.07 wt% to 0.27 wt% and corresponding to 97.1% Al removal. In addition, a similar trend can also be observed from the P removal, where almost 80% of P was removed from an initial 12.5 ppmw to 2.5 ppmw after acid treatment. Assuming all the Ca and Al are from the two main precipitates, CaSi_2 and CaAl_2Si_2 ; thus, the leachability of the two phases in Si-Ca-Al alloy can be obtained by converting the Ca and Al concentration to the two silicides. As shown in Figure 6, the results also demonstrate that the two phases are highly reactive, and CaSi_2 exhibits slightly higher leachability than the CaAl_2Si_2 phase.

Figure 5: Concentration of remaining impurities and impurities removal degree leached by 10% HCl at 60 °C for 3 h, initial particle size: 1-5 mm.

The removal degree of impurities after 3 hours of leaching is presented in Figure 7. It can be seen that nearly all Ca, Mg, and Al can be removed, while the removal of transition metal impurities is around 60-70%. The main reason is attributed to the transition metal impurities gathered in the Fe_3Si_7 phase, which has poor leachability in the HCl solution. Thus, those impurities were physically separated when the surrounded leachable phases all dissolved. Consequently, the removal efficiency of the transition metal impurities becomes lower than that of the impurities of the leachable phase. Nevertheless, it is also worth noting that there was no sieving process performed in the present study after leaching, which means that some transition metal silicides may also exist in the final products and therefore lower the removal efficiency.

Figure 6: Calculated removal degree of the main precipitates CaSi_2 and CaAl_2Si_2 .

Figure 7: Impurity removal degree of studied Si-Ca-Al alloy leached by 10% HCl at 60 °C for 3 h, initial particle size: 1-5 mm.

Si recovery is an important parameter for Si production from the SiAl process. In this work, the Si recovery rate was calculated according to the following formula:

$$\zeta = \frac{m_{\text{after leaching}}}{M_{\text{initial pure Si phase}}} \times 100\% \quad [4]$$

where $m_{\text{after leaching}}$ denotes the materials obtained after the leaching process and $M_{\text{initial pure Si phase}}$ indicates the weight of the Si phase in the Si-Ca-Al alloy, while the weight of the main silicides CaSi_2 , CaAl_2Si_2 , and Fe_3Si_7 are excluded.

The weight percentage of each phase can be estimated based on the elemental concentration from Table I by assuming the alloy is a Si-Ca-Al-Fe pseudo system and each precipitate contains only insignificant impurities. The calculation process is shown below:

$$\omega_{CaAl_2Si_2} \approx \omega_{Al\ element} \times \frac{M_{CaAl_2Si_2}}{2M_{Al}} = 9.07\% \times \frac{150}{54} = 25.19\% \quad [5]$$

$$\omega_{CaSi_2} \approx \left(\omega_{Ca\ element} - \frac{M_{Ca}}{M_{CaAl_2Si_2}} \omega_{CaAl_2Si_2} \right) \times \frac{M_{CaSi_2}}{M_{Ca}} = 8.18\% \times \frac{96}{40} = 19.63\% \quad [6]$$

$$\omega_{Fe_3Si_7} \approx \omega_{Fe\ element} \times \frac{M_{Fe_3Si_7}}{3M_{Fe}} = 0.46\% \times \frac{364}{168} = 1.0\% \quad [7]$$

$$\omega_{Si\ phase} \approx 1 - \omega_{CaAl_2Si_2} - \omega_{CaSi_2} - \omega_{Fe_3Si_7} = 54.18\% \quad [8]$$

where ω_i denotes the weight percentage of the specific phase or element and M_i indicates the atomic or molecular mass.

According to the above calculation, the weight percentage of the pure Si phase is 54.18%. Since the initial charged alloy is 10.00 g and there were in total 4.44 g leached samples collected after leaching and drying. Thus, the corresponding Si recovery rate is obtained as 81.9%. It has been widely reported that the reaction of the $CaSi_2$ phase with acids is also associated with the cracking effect of leaching particles (Lynch, 2009; Fang *et al.*, 2014). Thus, as a result, fine Si particles were generated and parts of them were lost in the post-cleaning and washing process since the leaching solution was directly poured out and without filtration treatment.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the microstructure and acid leaching experiment of a Si-Ca-Al alloy produced from SisAl pilot scale aluminothermic reduction were studied in lab scale. The main results are summarize as follows:

1. The Si-Ca-Al alloy contains precipitates of $CaSi_2$ and $CaAl_2Si_2$, and with minor Fe-bearing phases embedded inside them.
2. Acid leaching results indicate that 97.5% Ca and 97.1% Al can be leached, while 79.8% P removal achieved after 3 hours HCl leaching at 60 °C with magnetic stirring.
3. The present leaching experiments show Si purity can be upgraded from 75% to over 99% with a Si recovery about 80%.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research leading to these results has been performed within the SisAl Pilot project (<https://www.sisal-pilot.eu/> (accessed on 1 April 2022)) and received funding from the European Community's Horizon 2020 Programme (H2020/2014-2020) under grant agreement No 869268.

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